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Research Article

ANTIBIOTIC SUSCEPTIBILITY PATTERN OF BACTERIAL ISOLATES FROM SURFACES OF VARIOUS REFRIGERATED AND NON-REFRIGERATED CANNED DRINKS SOLD WITHIN ABAKALIKI METROPOLIS**Okonkwo Eucharia Chinyere, Ndukwe Emmanuel Chisom, Agah Maduka Victor, Idioha Jude Chinedu and Nwachi Anthonia Chinyere.**

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Abstract:

The antibiotic susceptibility profile of bacterial isolates from the surfaces of various refrigerated and non-refrigerated canned drinks sold within Abakaliki metropoli were evaluated in this study. Standard bacteriological culture-based techniques, employing the use of media including: Nutrient broth, Nutrient agar, Mannitol salt agar, Cetrimide agar, Salmonella-Shigella agar and MacConkey agar were used for culture and isolation of bacteria while microscopy and biochemical analysis were employed for identification. A total of 80 canned drinks surfaces were swabbed and subjected to analysis. Kirby-Bauer disc diffusion technique was used for antibacterial susceptibility testing. The multiple antibiotic resistance index (MARI) was deduced from the antibiogram characterization to evaluate the public health importance of the bacterial isolates. Refrigerated samples had a frequency occurrence of 28.6% contamination while 71.4% contamination was observed for non-refrigerated samples. The bacterial species isolated include Staphylococcus aureus 14 (40%), Pseudomonas aeruginosa 8 (23.8%), Escherichia coli 10 (28.6%) and Salmonella species 3 (8.6%). The isolates were most susceptible to Ciprofloxacin (93.8%) and Gentamicin (85.2%) and least susceptible to Cefixime (22.1%) and Cefuroxime (30.3%). The outcome of the investigation revealed that the surfaces of canned drinks sold in many open markets to both direct and indirect consumers are possibly contaminated with microorganisms. It is recommended to clean the top surfaces of canned drinks before drinking to reduce risk of bacterial contaminants.

Key words: Antibiotic, Refrigerated, Non-refrigerated, Canned Drinks, contamination

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INTRODUCTION:

A beverage can is a metal container designed to hold a fixed portion of liquid such as carbonated soft drinks, alcoholic drinks, fruit juices, teas, herbal teas, energy drinks, etc. The surfaces of canned drinks have been muted as a carrier of microorganisms particularly bacteria which are ubiquitous in nature (Ogofure *et al.*, 2018). These bacteria have also been implicated as a cause of some serious health challenges particularly for immunocompromised individuals with multiple antibiotic resistance index of the isolated bacteria from canned drinks and wines surfaces (Ogofure *et al.*, 2018). There have been several reports on the contamination of surfaces of objects by bacteria ranging from computer keyboards; to automated teller machine keypads (Kapdi *et al.*, 2008; Famurewa and David, 2009; Onochie *et al.*, 2013; Kigigha and Jonathan, 2017; Akinnibosun and Adetitun, 2018). More so, there are several other studies which have shown the ubiquity of microorganisms in connection to public health in that they are able to colonize or contaminate other surfaces such as mobile phones of hospital staff (Kilic *et al.*, 2009), beverage packages (Dantas *et al.*, 2006) as well as food and household surfaces (Kusumaningrum *et al.*, 2002; Othman, 2015). The quantitative analysis of bacteria from aforementioned inanimate objects exist for studies but there are not many studies which have tried to estimate the population of certain species of bacteria on the surface of canned drink samples.

Microbial attachment to surfaces is a potential way of transmission of pathogens in food processing industry, catering and the domestic environment (Giauris and Nychas, 2006; Simoes *et al.*, 2010; Kuda *et al.*, 2015). Contaminations can be an intermediate step in transmission of pathogens from their original habitat in the environment to food contact surfaces (Reij *et al.*, 2004; Silva and Martinis, 2013; Valero *et al.*, 2017). Exposure of pathogens on surfaces of canned drinks samples may take place either by direct contact with contaminated objects or indirectly through airborne particles. Several studies indicated that various bacteria, including *Escherichia coli*, *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Salmonella* species survive on hands, can drinks surfaces, sponges/cloths and utensils for hours or days after initial contact with the microorganisms (Kusumaningrum *et al.*, 2002; Kusumaningrum *et al.*, 2003). Rodents are common to these spaces, as they are difficult to seal and often contain moisture that is attractive to pests (Michaels *et al.*, 2003). Cockroaches are known to carry *Salmonella* spp. and it is believed that they may represent reservoirs capable of spreading this organism to food products (Michaels *et al.*, 2003). Dust on canned drinks and wines could also represent

a potential infection hazard, as *Salmonella* spp. have been found viable in dust for up to 10 months (Michaels *et al.*, 2003). Even though the cans are produced under hygienic conditions, they are exposed to some bacteria and germs during storage period, transportation and service. The risk of beverage cans to come in contact with rats, bugs, and other germs where they are stored is high (Ayçiçek and Küçükkaarslan, 2003). Dirt accumulation of long-term storage, various abuse conditions described above, or even dripping of meat juices, is known to occur.

Microbes are extremely adaptable to conditions and survive everywhere including canned drink surfaces. Researchers have discovered that dust on canned drink surfaces could represent a potential infection hazard, as *Salmonella specie* have been found viable in dust for up to 10 months (Michaels *et al.*, 2003). Even though the cans are produced under hygienic conditions, they are exposed to some bacteria and germs during storage period, handling, transportation and services. Individuals who handle these drinks from various locations maybe potential carriers of microorganisms, which therefore enhances the risk of contamination from microbes present on canned drink surfaces. Consequently there is the possibility for microbes to be introduced into humans through consumption of these drinks to cause them illnesses of different degrees.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Study Design

The study was designed in such a way that a total of eighty (80) samples were collected from retailshops, and wholesale distributors in Abakaliki metropolis. For every store or shops, 20 sets of samples were obtained (10 from on display and 10 from refrigerator, excluding wholesale distributors where 20 samples were obtained from the crates).

Sample collection

The samples were collected from the various stipulated site's in Abakaliki metropolis. Moistened swab sticks were used to swab the upper surfaces of canned drinks which comes in direct contact with the mouth. A total of eighty (80) samples from four different locations were evaluated in this research. Thirty (30) samples were collected from refrigerator and fifty (50) from non-refrigerated/on-display and labeled. The swabs were transported to the Microbiology laboratory unit of Ebonyi State University Abakaliki within 1 hour for bacteriological analysis.

Bacteriological analysis

The samples swabs were cultured at 37°C for 24 hours in a test tubes containing 5ml Nutrient broth for enrichment. Thereafter, the samples were streaked onto Nutrient agar, Mannitol salt agar, Cetrimide agar, MacConkey agar and Salmonella-Shigella agar at 37°C for 24 hours. The discrete colonies were subcultured severely to obtain pure cultures that were identified and characterised on the basis of morphological characterization and biochemical tests (Oxoid UK 2006).

Antibiotics Susceptibility Test

Antibiotic susceptibility testing was carried out using the standard Kirby-Bauer disc diffusion technique (Bauer, 2006).

Multiple Antibiotic Resistance (MAR) Index

The multiple antibiotic resistance MAR index was determined for each isolate using the methods delineated by Chitanand *et al.* (2010) by dividing the percentage of antibiotic resistance of the total percentage of antibiotics used in the study. Expressed mathematically A/B (Where A = Total number of antibiotics the isolates were resistant to and B = Total number of antibiotics tested).

Statistical analysis

The obtained data in this research were exposed to version 21.0 of SPSS statistical package. Descriptive statistics was employed to both determine the level of contamination as well as the susceptibility profile of obtained isolates.

RESULTS:

Morphology and Biochemical characteristics of bacteria isolated from surfaces of canned drinks sold within Abakaliki Metropolis

The morphology and biochemical characteristics of bacteria isolated from surfaces of canned drinks sold within Abakaliki metropolis is shown in Table 1. It revealed the colour, shape, Gram staining reaction as well as the biochemical characteristics of the following identified isolates; *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Escherichia coli*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and *Salmonella* species.

Bacterial distribution from the surfaces of canned drinks from various study locations and shops in Abakaliki metropolis

The prevalence of bacteria from the surfaces of several canned drinks sold in Abakaliki is shown in Table 2 and it revealed that *Staphylococcus aureus* was the most common bacterium isolated from the samples.

Percentage occurrence of bacteria isolated from surfaces of refrigerated and non-refrigerated canned drinks sold within Abakaliki Metropolis

The percentage occurrence of bacterial isolates from surfaces of refrigerated and non refrigerated canned drinks sold in Abakaliki metropolis is shown in Table 3. It revealed that *Escherichia coli* was the highest isolated organism from the refrigerated canned drinks with a frequency of 5 (14.3%) while *Staphylococcus aureus* was the highest isolated organism from non-refrigerated canned drinks with a frequency of 14 (40%).

Antibiotic susceptibility and resistance pattern of bacteria isolated from surfaces of canned drinks sold within Abakaliki Metropolis

The antibiotic sensitivity and resistance pattern of isolated bacteria from the surfaces of canned drinks is shown in Table 4. It revealed that *S. aureus* was 100% susceptible to Ciprofloxacin and 14.3% least susceptible to Cefuroxime, *P. aeruginosa* was 75% susceptible to Ciprofloxacin and 0.0% least susceptible to Cefotaxim and Cefuroxim, *E. coli* was 100% susceptible to Ciprofloxacin and 20% least susceptible to Vancomycin and *Salmonella* species was 100% susceptible to Ciprofloxacin, Ceftriaxone, Gentamycin and Cephazolin and 33.3% least susceptible to Erythromycin.

Determination of Multiple Antibiotic resistance index (MARI) exhibited by bacteria isolated from surfaces of canned drinks sold within Abakaliki Metropolis

The multiple antibiotic resistance index was observed among the isolate with MARI value of 0.8, 0.9, 0.8 and 0.6 exhibited by bacteria isolated from the surfaces of canned drinks as shown in Table 5.

Table 1: Morphological, Microscopic and Biochemical Characteristics of Bacterial Isolates from surfaces of canned drinks sold within Abakaliki Metropolis

Morphological characteristics			Microscopic characteristics		Biochemical tests				Suspected organisms
Shape	Colour	Media	GramRXN	Motility test	OX	IN	CAT	CIT	
Rod	Pink	MacConkey agar	-	+	-	-	+	-	<i>Escherichia coli</i>
Rod	Black	Salmonella-Shigella agar	-	+	-	-	+	+	<i>Salmonella spp.</i>
Cocci	Yellow	Mannitol salt agar	+	-	-	-	+	+	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>
Rod	Green	Cetrimide agar	-	+	+	-	+	+	<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>

KEY: IN = Indole, OX = Oxidase, CAT = Catalase, CIT = Citrate test, Gram RXN = Gram staining reaction.

2: Bacterial distribution from the surfaces of canned drinks from various study locations and shops in Abakaliki metropolis

S/N	Samples and locations (n=5)	Isolated organisms
1	Kpiri-Kpiri (S 1)	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> and <i>E. coli</i> ,
2	Kpiri-Kpiri (S 2)	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> , <i>E. coli</i> and <i>Salmonella</i> species
3	Kpiri-Kpiri (S 3)	<i>Escherichia coli</i> , <i>P. aeruginosa</i> and <i>S. aureus</i>
4	Kpiri-Kpiri (S 4)	<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i> and <i>E. coli</i>
5	Mile 50 (S 1)	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> , <i>P. aeruginosa</i> and <i>E. coli</i>
6	Mile 50 (S 2)	<i>P. aeruginosa</i> and <i>E. coli</i>
7	Mile 50 (S 3)	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> and <i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>
8	Mile 50 (S 4)	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> and <i>E. coli</i>
9	Ogoja road (S 1)	<i>S. aureus</i> and <i>E. coli</i>
10	Ogoja road (S 2)	<i>S. aureus</i> , <i>P. aeruginosa</i> , <i>E. coli</i> and <i>Salmonella</i> species
11	Ogoja road (S 3)	<i>S. aureus</i> and <i>E. coli</i>
12	Ogoja road (S 4)	<i>S. aureus</i> and <i>Salmonella</i> species
13	Warehouse 1 (10)	-
14	Warehouse 2 (10)	-

KEY: S = Shops, n = 5 for each shop and 10 for each warehouse.

Table 3: Percentage occurrence of bacterial isolates from surfaces of refrigerated and non-refrigerated canned drinks sold within Abakaliki Metropolis

S/N	Isolates (n=35)	Percentage occurrence of the isolates from Refrigerated canned drinks (%)	Percentage occurrence of the isolates from Non-refrigerated canned drinks (%)
1	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	-	14 (40)
2	<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	4 (11.4)	4 (11.4)
3	<i>Escherichia coli</i>	5 (14.3)	5 (14.3)
4	<i>Salmonella</i> species	1 (2.9)	2 (5.7)
	Total	10 (28.6%)	25 (71.4%)

Table 4: Antibiotic susceptibility pattern of isolated bacteria from the surfaces of canned drinks

	CIP	AMP	CFM	CXM	E	CX	GN	VA	CZ	AML
<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> (14)	100	57.1	28.5	14.3	28.6	71.4	85.7	42.8	28.6	71.4
<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i> (8)	75.0	50.0	0.0	0.0	25.0	50.0	75.0	50.0	50.0	25.0
<i>Escherichia coli</i> (10)	100.0	40.0	60.0	40.0	60.0	60.0	80.0	20.0	20.0	40.0
<i>Salmonella species</i> (3)	100.0	66.7	70.0	66.7	33.3	100.0	100.0	66.7	100.0	66.7
Total (%)	93.8	53.5	22.1	30.3	36.7	70.4	85.2	44.9	49.7	50.8

KEY: CIP = Ciprofloxacin, AMP = Ampicillin, CFM = Cefotaxim, CXM = Cefuroxime, E = Erythromycin, CZ = Cephalosporin, GN = Gentamicin, VA = Vancomycin, CX = Ceftriaxone, AML = Anoxycillin

Table 5: Multiple antibiotic resistance index (MARI) exhibited by bacterial isolates from surfaces of canned drinks

Isolates	Antibiotics resistance patterns	INDEX VALUE
<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	AML, AMP, CFM, CXM, E, CN, VA, CZ	0.8
<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	CIP, AML, AMP, CFM, E, CRO, CN, VA, CZ	0.9
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	AML, AMP, CFM, CXM, E, CRO, CN, CZ	0.8
<i>Salmonella species</i>	AML, AMP, CFM, CXM, E, VA	0.6
AVERAGE MARI		0.78

KEY: CIP = Ciprofloxacin, AMP = Ampicillin, CFM = Cefotaxim, CXM = Cefuroxime, E = Erythromycin, CZ = Cephalosporin, GN = Gentamicin, VA = Vancomycin, CX = Ceftriaxone, AML = Anoxycillin

DISCUSSION:

This study has shown that surfaces of canned drinks can be readily contaminated irrespective of whether they are kept in the refrigerator or not (Table 2). The isolated organisms in this study were identified to be *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Samonella species*, and *Escherichia coli*. It has been reported that some of these identified pathogens can survive on hands, sponges and surfaces of stainless steel materials for several days and weeks after contact (Kusumaningrum *et al.*, 2002). Some bacteria, such as *Escherichia coli*, *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* may either directly contaminate surfaces or indirectly do same through aerosolized droplets and could on external beverage packaging materials (Dantaset *et al.*, 2006) for up to several days after contact. However, most contamination could be attributed to environmental influences such as personal hygiene of handlers, presence aerosolized droplets in the storage environment and contamination from other sources.

More so, the fact that most Gram-positive bacteria, such as *Staphylococcus aureus* contaminate inanimate environment has been well established. They can survive for months on inanimate surfaces as reported by Ekrami *et al.*, (2010); and this is in agreement with the results obtained from this study as

the study surfaces have stayed on stores for days or weeks. From this study, samples collected refrigerator and non refrigerator was compared to determine which source that had the most contamination and it was established that out of the 80 samples analyzed, non-refrigerated samples had the most percentage occurrence of bacteria at 71.4%. And these findings agreed with the work of (Abraham *et al.*, 2018) who reported the isolation of certain microorganisms from the refrigerator. This could be due to the samples being exposed to dust and rodents such as cockroaches, as the samples are being stored on shelves in the shops. The surface contamination observed is a clear reflection of the poor hygienic practices of the vendors as well as the surrounding environmental conditions which favour the survival and proliferation of the bacterial pathogens.

Other frequently occurring bacteria like *Escherichia coli* and *Samonella* have been associated with diarrhea; and could get to the surfaces of canned drinks either through food products stored in the refrigerator or as a result of vendor's poor personal hygiene practices. And these findings agrees with the work of (Abraham *et al.*, 2018) who reported the Qualitative Detection and Isolation of Bacteria from

Surfaces of Canned Drinks sold in Ugbor, Benin City.

The presence of *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* could be attributed to improperly packed food sources. This organism has been shown to grow inside the refrigerator due to incessant power outage and inconsistent power supply not forgetting the fact that most times, most of these refrigerators are not adequately sanitized. And this findings agrees with the work of (Otu-Bassey *et al.*, 2017) who reported the isolation of certain microorganisms from the refrigerator. More so, It was observed during this study that the isolated organisms may pose a big health challenge and food safety as most of the isolates were highly resistant against some antibiotics such as Cefotaxim, Cefuroxime, erythromycin, vancomycin etc. The MAR index according to Chitanand *et al.*, (2010) reflected the organism's importance as a public health threat. Table 5 from this research revealed that the isolated organisms were of public health importance and that they have been shown to be multi-resistant pathogens.

Recommendations

Based on the findings from this study, it is important to thoroughly wash the top surfaces of these canned drinks with clean water before consumption and also for vendors to sanitize the refrigerator especially those that preserve meats and other perishable food products in the fridge. Vendors should also practice good personal hygiene in dealing with their products. More so, patients infected through consumption of these drinks should make use of appropriate antibiotics for treatment of these bacteria.

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